

Synthesis of hydroxyapatite by sol-gel combustion method using tricarboxylic acid and diamide as a mixed fuel

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Abstract : Calcium hydroxyapatite was synthesized by sol-gel combustion method by employing urea and citric acid as a mixed fuel. Nitric acid was used as an oxidizer; calcium nitrate and di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate were taken as the calcium and phosphate precursor respectively. The influence of metal ion to fuel ratio on the phase evolution and morphology was studied. The synthesized powders were characterized by powder X-ray diffractometer for phase evolution and Fourier transform infrared spectrometer was used to find out the carbonate substitution in hydroxyl and phosphate sites. Thermal analysis was carried out to verify the phase transitions and thermal stability of the products. The result shows the influence of ratio of fuels on the auto ignition temperature as the auto ignition temperature of urea decreases by the addition of citric acid. In addition, the phase formation is found to vary with the metal ion to fuel ratio, irrespective of the initial metal ion to phosphate ratio.

Keywords : Biomaterials, self-propagating synthesis, phase transformation, X-ray diffraction.

Introduction

Synthetic calcium hydroxyapatite has almost the same chemical composition as human bone¹ and possesses excellent biocompatibility and bioactivity². Hydroxyapatite present in natural bone is non-stoichiometric with Na⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Sr²⁺ ions substituted in calcium sites and F⁻, Cl⁻ ions in hydroxyl site³ whereas CO₃²⁻ ion can get substituted in both hydroxyl and phosphate sites⁴. Due to these considerations, it is difficult to exactly mimic the natural hydroxyapatite in every aspect. As a biomaterial used in load bearing applications, the bioactivity and mechanical property of the synthesized hydroxyapatite is highly significant. Specifically, the mechanical property of synthesized hydroxyapatite is poor when compared with the natural hydroxyapatite⁵. The physical characteristics of synthesized hydroxyapatite such as morphology, size and crystallinity decide its mechanical properties. Similarly bioactivity in physiological environment of pure hydroxyapatite differs from carbonate substituted hydroxyapatite (CHAP) as the dissolution of carbonate substituted hydroxyapatite is more rapid than the pure hydroxyapatite⁶. Hence, for permanent structures such as

coatings, the insoluble form of hydroxyapatite is used and for temporary structures like bone cement, the soluble form of hydroxyapatite is used⁷. In addition to the biomedical applications, it is also used in the field of catalysis⁸, chemical and biosensors⁹⁻¹¹, adsorbent¹² and chromatographic separations¹³. Hence the synthesis of hydroxyapatite with different morphology and substitution at various sites has been of interest to researchers for a long time.

Sol-gel method based on mixed complexing agents like EDTA-citrate complexing process results in nanocrystalline powder with high surface area¹⁴. Also addition of nitric acid during EDTA-citrate complexing process results in the size reduction of the crystallites. The drawback of sol-gel synthesis is the expensive starting materials, long time duration for synthesis and the various steps involved in the synthesis whereas the sol-gel combustion method is less expensive, less time consuming and is also a one step synthesis. In order to facilitate all these advantages we modified the existing sol-gel combustion method in the present investigation by means of adding mixed complexing agents with different func-

tional groups as a fuel which is expected to form a different gel network for different ratios and which will alter the physical characteristics of the product. Organic substances reported as fuel in combustion synthesis were citric acid, tartaric acid, succinic acid, glycine, urea, hydrazine and sucrose. When carboxylic acids are used, precipitation of metal ions can be prevented due to the stronger complexing ability of carboxylic acid functional groups with metal ions hence the compositional homogeneity of the constituents is maintained. Whereas amine group-containing fuels like glycine and hydrazine were used as it decomposes at relatively low temperatures. Sucrose present in acid medium acts as a very good complexing agent and the powders produced were found to possess very high surface area but the disadvantage of using sucrose as a fuel is the removal of carbon particles in the product. When compared with carboxylic acids and sucrose, urea don't possess good complexing ability but the amount of CO₂ produced will be less when compared to the carboxylic acids and sucrose which will result in the pure hydroxyapatite formation whereas carbonaceous fuels may result in carbapatite. Citric acid and urea were chosen as the fuel based on their ability to form complex with metal ions and to act as a fuel. An objective of the present study is to optimize the ratio between citric acid and urea to form pure hydroxyapatite as the product and to study the effect of fuel ratio on the auto ignition temperature of the gel.

Experimental

Stoichiometric amount of powders of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (99%, AR, Rankem), (NH₄)₂HPO₄ (99%, AR, Merck), citric acid (99.7%, AR, SRL) and urea (99.5%, AR, Thomas Baker) were dissolved in the demineralized water at room temperature to yield 1 M stock solutions. The stock solutions of calcium nitrate, citric acid and urea were taken in different ratios in an uncovered glass beaker and stirred with a magnetic stirrer for 10 min at room temperature. The resultant solution was acidic with the pH of around 2 which was adjusted to the pH of around 10 using NH₄OH. Stoichiometric amount of (NH₄)₂HPO₄ solution is then added dropwise to the mixture under stirring condition which forms a gelatinous white precipitate. The precipitate formed was dissolved using concentrated nitric acid until the pH gets adjusted to 1. Now the

clear solution is stirred constantly, using magnetic stirrer and the temperature is raised to 70 °C and maintained for 2 h in an uncovered glass beaker. When the solution becomes highly viscous and transparent, the temperature is allowed to rise fast until the combustion reaction takes place. In order to facilitate proper combustion of fuel, sufficient supply of oxygen should be provided so that it is carried out in the open hot plate. Combustion takes place in the temperature range of 180 °C to 350 °C with continuous evolution of gases. The temperature at which the combustion takes place is measured by a thermocouple placed close to the surface of the gel. The precursor obtained is calcined at 900 °C for 2 h to result in hydroxyapatite.

Characterization :

Phase identification was done using RIKAKU X-Ray Diffractometer, using Cu K α , Ni filtered radiation. The functional groups were identified by using FTIR (Thermo Nicolet, Avatar 330 FTIR Spectrometer, USA) studies by KBr pellet method. The thermal analysis of the precursor was carried out at a heating rate of 20 °C/min in air from room temperature to 1000 °C using Thermal Analyzer (STA 409 C/CD, NETZSCH, Germany).

Results and discussion

The fuels used in the synthesis plays a dual role, as a complexing agent by preventing the precipitation of metal ions and acting as a fuel in the combustion reaction. The gel network formed for single fuel and mixed fuel will be totally different and it depends on the various functional groups present in the fuels. The energetics involved in the combustion will be different for single fuel and mixed fuels and hence the resultant product formed will not be the same for single fuel and mixed fuel. When urea is used as a single fuel it undergoes controlled hydrolysis to form ammonium hydroxide, which, on further reaction with metal ion, gives metal hydroxide¹⁵. Whereas the carboxylic acids like citric acid with more than two functional groups forms a cross linking polymeric network in which the metal ions are distributed homogeneously¹⁶. When these two complexing agents are mixed together, the reaction mechanism will not be the same as the one when they are used as a single fuel¹⁷. In addition, the resultant polymeric network formed for the mixed fuel

will be entirely different from single fuel which alters the distribution of metal ions in the polymeric network which decides the formation major phase. When the stoichiometric ratios of precursors and fuels were mixed with continuous stirring and the pH was adjusted to 10 by adding ammonium hydroxide solution, all samples were found to form a dense white precipitate which may be due to the formation of amorphous calcium phosphates. When the precipitate was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and the pH was adjusted to 1, it forms a very clear solution. The addition of ammonium hydroxide to the reaction mixture and further acidification with nitric acid serves two different purposes. The first purpose is the formation of ammonium nitrate which acts as a combustion aid during the vigorous redox reaction between the fuel and oxidant. The second purpose is to maintain the uniformity in the quantity of combustion aid and oxidant in all reactions. If the adjustment of pH is done by merely adding nitric acid, the quantity of oxidant added will be less for the sample containing more citric acid, as the carboxylic acid itself contributes some acidity to the sample hence to consumption of nitric acid will be less to attain the pH of 1.

When the solution is heated in hot plate for two hours, the solution got converted to a highly viscous transparent gel and further heating leads to evolution of large amount of fumes; and when the heating is continued, the gel undergoes a vigorous redox reaction with the oxidant and catches fire. The vigorous redox reaction between the gel network and oxidizer gives rise to a very high local temperature with the evolution of a large volume of gases. Though the temperature of hot plate was maintained at 300 °C, the particles could have attained higher local temperatures during ignition. A large amount of heat is released during the combustion which produces an in-

tense local heating that enhances the phase formation. The volume of gas generated and increase in the local temperature due to the combustion depend upon various factors such as nature of the gel network, temperature, water content and the ratio of fuels as the thermochemistry of combustion is different for different fuel combinations. The heat of combustion for the system depends on the nature of polymeric network formed during gelation and hence changes in the ratio of fuels. The change in polymeric network will in-turn changes the heat of combustion of the system which is evident from the experiment results in Table 1 showing the auto ignition temperature varies with the change in fuel ratio. The structure of the polymeric network formed by the organic molecules decides the morphology of the particles and the heat of combustion of the polymeric network decides the phase formation which is proved from the results tabulated (Table 1) where the phases formed are found to be different for different fuel ratios.

Table 1 shows that the auto ignition temperature is brought down drastically from 350 °C to 190 °C when the ratio of metal ion to urea is maintained constant along with all other experimental parameters and the ratio of citric acid alone is increased to two fold (CU 3) and three fold (CU 4). It is in agreement with the results reported for succinic acid-citric acid system where the addition of citric acid brings down the auto ignition temperature of succinic acid¹⁸. In the other way also, the auto ignition temperature comes down when the condition is reversed by means of maintaining the ratio of metal ion to citric acid constant along with all other experimental parameters remain the same and the ratio of urea alone increased to two fold (CU 5) and three fold (CU 6). It is reported elsewhere that if metal ion to urea ratio is higher than eight then there is no possibility of auto ignition¹⁹.

Table 1. Auto ignition temperature for various ratios of fuels

Sample name	Ratio of metal ion	Ratio of citric acid	Ratio of urea	Auto ignition temperature (°C)	Phases formed
CU 1	1	0.5	1	350	β-TCP, HAP
CU 2	1	1	5	350	B-TCP, HAP
CU 3	1	2	5	180	B-TCP, HAP
CU 4	1	3	5	190	B-TCP, HAP
CU 5	1	1	10	300	HAP
CU 6	1	1	15	220	β-TCP

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of the precursors synthesized using citric acid and urea as a mixed fuel.

But from the observations it is proved that auto ignition can be induced by means of adding a small quantity of citric acid to the mixture containing high metal ion to urea ratio. This may be due to the highly oxidizable linkages present in the citric acid molecule. It is also observed that when the citric acid ratio is more, then the auto ignition temperature is close to the auto ignition temperature of citric acid and if the ratio of urea is more, then the auto ignition temperature is close to the auto ignition temperature of urea. But in general, the auto ignition temperature pattern varies randomly with different ratios of fuels and does not show any continuous increasing or decreasing trend with increase in the ratio of any of the fuel content in the mixture.

FTIR spectra (Fig. 1) of the as synthesized precursors shows the stretching and bending vibrations corresponding to a weak OH⁻ bands (631 and 3571 cm⁻¹) and PO₄³⁻

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of the precursors synthesized using citric acid and urea as a mixed fuel.

(570, 602, 1045, 1089 cm⁻¹) vibrations, together with the weak bands of the CO₃²⁻ group (875, 1440 and 1633 cm⁻¹). Carbonate can substitute in Ca₁₀(OH)₂(PO₄)₆ on two possible sites which are distinguished by FT-IR spectroscopy. Intense peak at 1440 cm⁻¹ and a less intense peak 875 cm⁻¹ indicate the substitution of carbonate ions in phosphate site (site B) and broad band at 1633 cm⁻¹ indicates that OH site (site A) is also substituted with carbonate ion. A high intense shoulder peak at 1384 cm⁻¹ and 2015 cm⁻¹ may be due to the organic constituents left out without any decomposition. XRD patterns (Fig. 2) of the as synthesized precursors confirms the phase formation during combustion. Even though the experimental parameters used in all the systems remain the same the product formed is found to be different for various fuel ratios. This in turn confirms the prediction based on the auto ignition temperature that the energetics of the system depends on the ratio of fuels used. Due to the change in energetics of the different systems, the auto ignition temperature of the system changes, which in turn varies

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of the product synthesized using citric acid and urea as a mixed fuel.

the intensity of local temperature during combustion and leads to the formation of different phases for different ratios of fuels.

FTIR spectra (Fig. 3) of the calcined samples shows the absence of bending and stretching vibrations of hydroxyl group for CU 6 sample which indicates the absence of hydroxyapatite phase. B type carbonate substitution is shown by CU 1 and CU 4 samples which may be due to the higher carbon content of citric acid molecule present in higher ratios in these samples. Whereas CU 4 sample shows less intense bending and stretching vibrations of hydroxyl group which indicates the ratio of hydroxyapatite phase is less in the resultant product when compared with other samples. The system with low auto ignition temperature (CU 3 and CU 4) forms an amorphous product whereas all other samples form a well crystalline product. This may be due to high local tempera-

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of the product synthesized using citric acid and urea as a mixed fuel.

ture attained due to high auto ignition temperature which influences the crystallization of the product. The major phase of all systems was found to be hydroxyapatite and in most of the systems β -tricalcium phosphate is found to be the secondary phase. Calcium carbonate phase is found to be the secondary phase in the system where the urea content is very high when compared with other systems.

XRD patterns (Fig. 4) of the samples calcined at 900 °C for two hours confirms the results obtained from FTIR spectra as it shows the absence of hydroxyapatite phase for CU 6 system. The hydroxyapatite and calcium carbonate phases found in precursor were found to be totally absent in the calcined product which may be due to the influence of calcium carbonate in the decomposition of hydroxyapatite. Except CU 1 and CU 5 all other samples contain β -TCP as an impure phase and its content is comparatively higher in CU 4 sample. Pure hydroxyapatite phase is observed for CU 5 sample whereas CU 1 sample is found to have hydroxyapatite phase with B type carbonate substitution which is evident from its XRD

Fig. 5. Thermal analysis pattern of the precursor prepared from 1 : 10 ratio of citric acid and urea as a mixed fuel.

pattern and FTIR spectra. Whereas the XRD pattern (Fig. 2) of CU 6 precursor shows hydroxyapatite as the major phase but the calcined product of CU 6 sample shows β -TCP as the major phase. The reason may be the less thermal stability of carbonated hydroxyapatite. Anna Slosarczyk *et al.*²⁰ reported the thermal stability and decomposition mechanism of carbonated hydroxyapatites. When the CO_3^{2-} ions replaces the PO_4^{3-} ion, there is an increase in Ca/P ratio which leads to the non-stoichiometric carbonated apatites which are thermally less stable than the pure hydroxyapatite. Hence the presence of carbonate ions in the structure lowers thermal stability of hydroxyapatite resulting in its decomposition in the temperature range of 800–900 °C leading to β -tricalcium phosphate as the secondary phase.

TGA curve of the thermal analysis (Fig. 5) of the CU 5 precursor shows a major mass loss of 8.5% between 50 °C and 200 °C which is due to the dehydration of water molecules from the precursor. The second mass loss of 8.7% between 200 °C and 400 °C is due to the decomposition of the leftout fuel present in the precursor. The third mass loss of 3.5% between 450 °C and 900 °C is due to the decomposition of the carbonaceous substances left out after the decomposition of precursor. DTA curves

show exothermic peaks at 175 °C due to the decomposition of leftout fuel present in the precursor and the peak at 425 °C is due to the removal of carbonaceous constituents present in the precursor. The peak at 677 °C may be due to the removal of carbonate ions from the hydroxyapatite phase and the transformation of nonstoichiometric hydroxyapatite to pure hydroxyapatite.

Conclusion :

It is concluded from the above studies that the ratio of citric acid to urea is an important parameter which plays a major role in the phase formation. It is evident from the above work, that addition of citric acid not only brings down the auto ignition temperature of urea but also enhances the auto ignition tendency of urea. The results indicate that using appropriate amount of citric acid and urea as fuel will result in hydroxyapatite as a major phase and whereas all other ratios will result in the formation of composites containing both hydroxyapatite and β -tricalcium phosphate and if higher content of calcium carbonate is formed as a secondary phase, then it will lead to the decomposition of hydroxyapatite during calcination.

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